

Clinical Characteristics and Comorbidity patterns for Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder (DMDD) in Mexican Adolescents: Epidemiological Study

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ABSTRACT

Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder (DMDD) is a diagnosis in the DSM-5 based on limited research in samples mostly from the U.S.

Objective: To evaluate the DMDD diagnosis in a Mexican adolescent sample by assessing its clinical characteristics and delimitation from other disorders. A secondary objective was to evaluate the validity of the DSM-5 age of onset cut-off.

Method: This was a secondary data analysis of the Mexican Adolescent Mental Health survey, a household survey of 3,005 adolescents aged 12 to 17 years residing in Mexico City in 2005. Adolescents and one of their parents were interviewed with the Composite International Diagnostic Interview. A diagnostic algorithm for DMDD was developed *post hoc* using questions that map onto the DSM-5 criteria.

Results: Of the adolescents, 2.2% met the criteria for DMDD. This figure increased to 3.5% when raising the age of onset cut-off to 12 years. Of those meeting the DMDD criteria, 53.5% were male, 40.4% had used services for mental health problems, and 15.2% reported a suicide attempt. Most (94.3%) of those with DMDD had a comorbid disorder, disruptive behavioral disorders being the most frequent (86%).

Conclusions: The comorbidity pattern in this study suggests that DMDD is more clearly associated to the disruptive behavioral diagnostic category as a distinct disorder or a specifier than to the category encompassing depressive disorders. Raising the age-of-onset to 12 represents an important increase in the prevalence and may benefit an unattended group of chronically irritable youths with timely diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: *Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder; Epidemiological Study, Diagnosis.*

RESUMEN

Antecedentes: El trastorno disruptivo de la regulación emocional (TDRE) es un diagnóstico del DSM-5 basado en investigaciones limitadas en muestras principalmente de los EE. UU. **Objetivo:** Evaluar el diagnóstico de TDRE en una muestra de adolescentes mexicanos mediante la evaluación de sus características clínicas y la delimitación de otros trastornos. Un objetivo secundario fue evaluar la validez de la edad de inicio del DSM-5. **Método.** Este fue un análisis de datos secundarios de la encuesta de salud mental de adolescentes mexicanos, una encuesta de hogares de 3005 adolescentes de 12 a 17 años

que residían en la Ciudad de México en 2005. Los adolescentes y uno de sus padres fueron entrevistados con la Entrevista Diagnóstica Internacional Compuesta. Se desarrolló un algoritmo diagnóstico para TDRE post hoc utilizando preguntas que se asignan a los criterios del DSM-5. **Resultados.** De los adolescentes, el 2,2% cumplió con los criterios para TDRE. Esta cifra aumenta al 3,5% cuando se aumenta la edad de inicio a 12 años. De aquellos que cumplían los criterios de TDRE, el 53,5% eran varones, el 40,4% había utilizado servicios para problemas de salud mental y el 15,2% informó un intento de suicidio. La mayoría (94,3%) de aquellos con TDRE tenían un trastorno comórbido, siendo los trastornos de conducta disruptiva los más frecuentes (86%). **Conclusiones.** El patrón de comorbilidad en este estudio sugiere que el TDRE está más claramente asociado a la categoría diagnóstica de conducta disruptiva como un trastorno distinto o un especificador que a la categoría que abarca los trastornos depresivos. Aumentar la edad de inicio a 12 años representa un aumento importante en la prevalencia y puede beneficiar a un grupo de jóvenes crónicamente irritables desatendidos con un diagnóstico y tratamiento oportunos.

Palabras clave: *Trastorno disruptivo de la regulación emocional, irritabilidad, nosología, comorbilidad.*

INTRODUCTION

Diagnostic controversy

Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder (DMDD) is a diagnosis in the DSM-5, incorporated into the depressive disorders section. It is characterized by frequent, severe, and recurrent temper outbursts

(criterion A) and chronically irritable and/or angry mood (criterion D). Both criteria need to be present at least one year and these manifestations must appear before the age of 10 while diagnosis can be made only between the ages of 6 and 18 (1).

The DMDD as an independent diagnostic category has been criticized because chronic irritability, its main feature, is also present in several different psychiatric disorders (2,3). Moreover, there has been a proposal to consider chronic irritability as a dimension phenotype cutting across diagnoses (3,4,5); this concept is consistent with the Research Domain Criteria (RDoC) of the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) that suggest that mechanisms of psychopathology and novel treatment need to be studied across diagnostic boundaries (5). Another controversial point is the DMDD 10-year cut-off: there is only evidence for forward developmental trajectories in conduct disorder for aggressive behaviors, but not in categories associated with irritability (6,7). One of the principal goals of proposing this diagnostic category was to reduce the inappropriate rate of bipolar disorder diagnosis in children and adolescents with this broad bipolar phenotype (2), even though evidence from community and clinical longitudinal studies show that this phenotype is associated with later unipolar depression and anxiety disorders, rather than bipolar depression (8-10).

Severe Mood Dysregulation Disorder and Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder

Few studies have examined the proposed DMDD diagnosis and criteria, fundamentally because this disorder was elaborated from a previous diagnostic construct called Severe Mood Dysregulation (SMD). SMD is similar to DMDD, sharing two of the three

core diagnostic features. SMD included criteria A and D from DMDD, but also required symptoms of chronic hyperarousal such as distractibility, flight of ideas, racing thoughts, pressured speech, insomnia, and agitation. The SMD criteria included a 12-year age-of-onset cutoff, inconsistent with the 10-year threshold established for DMDD (11). It is important to note that research on SMD comes basically from one group at the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) in the USA, which has documented that youths with SMD present a distinct phenotype from youths with bipolar disorder and are characterized with a high lifetime comorbidity with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and oppositional defiant disorder (ODD), and a higher risk for unipolar depressive disorder than bipolar disorder in adulthood (12).

Validity and Reliability of Disruptive Mood Dysregulation Disorder

Post hoc analyses of large datasets in which a proxy diagnosis of SMD is constructed retrospectively have been useful for providing evidence from non-clinical samples. A 3.3% lifetime prevalence of SMD was estimated from the Great Smoky Mountains Study (GSMS), 1.8% when restricted to those severely impaired. The GSMS included children and adolescents that were evaluated in two waves; during the first wave, mean age 10.6 years, children had more comorbid ADHD (26.9%), conduct disorder (CD) (25.9%) and ODD (24%) than affective disorders; in the second wave, mean age 18.3 years, adolescents diagnosed with SMD in the first wave were more likely to be diagnosed with a depressive disorder (odds ratio: 7.2) (13).

One of the first published studies on the DMDD using the DSM-5 proposed criteria in a clinical

sample found that 26% of patients met the DMDD criteria. However, there was little evidence that DMDD could be delimited from other disruptive disorders since 96% of those meeting the criteria also met the criteria for ODD or CD, and 77% met the criteria for ADHD and ODD or CD (2).

In one elegant integrated paper (8), three different retrospective studies were utilized to examine the relative utility of the DSM-5 DMDD proposed criteria in community samples of children: the Duke Preschool Anxiety Study (14), the GSMS (15) and the Caring for Children in the Community investigation (16). The DMDD prevalence rates ranged from 0.8% to 3.3% with the highest prevalence in preschoolers, even though this age group is excluded from DSM-5 criteria. The DMDD co-occurred with another disorder 62% to 92% of the time. The highest levels of co-occurrence were with depressive disorders (ORs between 9.9 and 23.5) and ODD (ORs between 52.9 and 103.0).

Interestingly, diverse data shows that pharmacological strategies tested for SMD and DMDD are more oriented to treat them as externalizing disorders. First, a monotherapy with a psychostimulant or an atypical antipsychotic like risperidone, already used in the treatment of severe irritability in youths with behavioral problems in developmental disorders; and second, the use of a serotonergic antidepressant as an add-on therapy in youths treated with a psychostimulant (17,18).

The DSM-5 Field Trials have been able to examine DMDD using original data and actual DSM-5 diagnoses. The interrater reliability for DMDD was found to be “unacceptable” at two of the three sites at which it was tested, yielding an overall “questionable” pooled kappa of 0.2519. This was the lowest

reliability estimate of any of the childhood diagnoses that were ultimately included in the DSM-5. All major reviews have been consistent in reporting lack of delimitation of DMDD with disruptive behavior disorders. External validity should be an important study objective for new diagnostic entities; to date there are few representative community studies of DMDD, even fewer in adolescent samples, and none, to our knowledge, that evaluate the diagnostic validity in Spanish speaking populations outside the United States. The estimated prevalence calculated for DMDD was 1.60% (95% CI, 0.28%–3.90%) for DMDD in a recent systematic review and meta-analysis that incorporated 41 studies (20).

OBJECTIVE

The aim of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic validity of DMDD with regards to two of the five phases of the systematic study proposed by Robins and Guze (21) to validate diagnostic classification in psychiatry, namely the clinical characteristics of those meeting the criteria for DMDD and delimitation from other disorders. A secondary objective was to evaluate the validity of the proposed age-of-onset cut-off by comparing prevalence, comorbidity pattern, and socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of those whose symptoms began before the age of 10 years, as is stipulated in the DSM-5 criteria, and those for whom the symptoms began between 10 and 12 years of age (extended period for school age children).

METHOD

Participants

This paper presents a secondary data analysis from the sample of the Mexican Adolescent Mental Health sur-

vey, a household survey conducted in 2005 of adolescents aged 12 to 17 years (22). This stratified multistage area probability sample of 3,005 adolescents is representative of the nearly two million adolescents residing in the Mexico City Metropolitan Area at the time. For 2,847 of these adolescents, one of their parents or guardians was also interviewed about their child's symptoms. For the purposes of this report all analyses are restricted to the 2,847 adolescents for whom parent reports are also available. In all strata, the primary sampling units were census count areas cartographically defined and updated for the XII Population and Housing Census in 2000. Secondary sampling units were city blocks (or groups of them) selected with probability proportional to size. All households within these city block units with adolescents in the age range were selected. One eligible member from each of these households was randomly selected using the Kish method of random number charts. The response rate of eligible respondents was 71%.

Procedures

A verbal and written explanation of the study was given to both parents and adolescents, after which a signed informed consent from a parent or legal guardian was obtained as well as the assent of the adolescent. Interviews were conducted in the homes of the selected participants. All study participants and their families were offered information on local mental health services. The Internal Review Board of the National Institute of Psychiatry approved the recruitment, consent and field procedures.

Measures

Adolescents were administered the fully structured, computer assisted, World Mental Health adolescent

version of the Composite International Diagnostic Interview (WMH-CIDI-A). Data on its development and validity is described elsewhere (23,24). The complementary CIDI parent interview was administered to a parent or guardian. Because the WMH-CIDI-A was developed before the DSM-5, not including DMDD, a diagnostic algorithm for DMDD was developed *post hoc*. Questions that map onto the DSM-5 criteria from the screening, depression, intermittent explosive disorder (IED) and ODD sections were used. CIDI questions were able to evaluate all criteria except criterion B which states that temper outbursts must be inconsistent with developmental level, and criterion E, the duration criterion stating that symptoms must be present for 12 months or more without any period lasting three or more months without symptoms. Both adolescent and parent reports of symptoms were combined such that the criterion was considered positive if either report endorsed the items in the criterion.

Criterion A was met by questions regarding anger attacks or tantrums when the participant broke something or hurt, hit, or threatened others. Criterion C was met by anger attacks involving slamming doors, breaking objects, hitting, and threatening others, that occurred 12 or more times a month or 3 or more times a week depending on the response options of each question. Criterion D was met by questions regarding being irritable, grumpy or in a bad mood most of the time. Criterion F was evaluated with the questions from the Sheehan Disability Scales imbedded in the CIDI in which the respondents, on a scale of zero to ten (0=no, 1-3=mild, 4-6=moderate, 7-9=severe and 10=very severe), rate how much the symptoms interfered with four different areas of life: household chores, school/work, family life and social life. Impairment was considered present with a rating

of one or more and severe with a rating of seven or more. In order to fulfill Criterion F, impairment was to be present in at least two areas and severe in at least one area. Finally, criterion J, which states that symptoms must not be better explained by other disorders, was operationalized by excluding all those who met criteria for bipolar I or II disorder ($n=75$); however, because of the objectives of this report, those meeting the criteria for ODD and IED were not excluded.

For all disorders other than DMDD, diagnostic classification was based on meeting the diagnostic criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition (25).

Statistical analysis

Data was weighted to adjust for differential probabilities of selection and non-response as well as post-stratification to the total Mexico City Metropolitan Area adolescent population according to the 2000 Census in the target age and sex range. The socio-demographic distribution of the sample closely approximated the target population such that roughly half were female, there was an even distribution of ages, two-thirds lived with both parents, and the socio-economic level of the parents represented the educational and income levels in Mexico. As a result of this complex sample design and weighting, estimates of standard errors for proportions were obtained with the Taylor series linearization method using the SUDAAN software (26). In order to compare socio-demographic and clinical characteristics and comorbidity patterns between those meeting the criteria for DMDD and other groups, multivariate logistic regression models were obtained also using SUDAAN software.

Ethical standards

This study was approved by the ethics committee of the National Institute of Psychiatry Ramón de la Fuente and, therefore, has been performed in accordance with the ethical standards set forth in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments. All participant-minors and their parents or legal guardians gave their assent/consent prior to their inclusion in the study.

RESULTS

Clinical and sociodemographic characteristics

Of this Mexican adolescent sample, 2.18% ($SE=0.22$) met the DSM-5 criteria for DMDD when combining the adolescent and parent report with an either/or rule. Those who met the criteria for DMDD reported moderate impairment on the Sheehan Disability Scales. The mean scores for impairment in household chores, school/work, family relations and social life were 4.3 ($SD = 0.3$), 3.6 ($SD = 0.4$), 4.9 ($SD = 0.4$) and 4.1 ($SD = 0.3$), respectively. Table 1 shows the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of those meeting the criteria for DMDD compared to the total sample. Of those meeting the DMDD criteria, 53.5% were male, 40.4% had used services for mental health problems at some point in their life, 27.9% reported lifetime suicidal behavior, and 15.2% a suicide attempt. The only significant difference between the DMDD sample and the total sample was the rate of adolescents living with both parents. Those meeting the DMDD criteria were 54% less likely to live with both parents than the general population sample ($aOR = 0.54$, 95% CI = 0.33- 0.88, $p= 0.01$).

Table 1. Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of those meeting the DMDD criteria compared to the total sample

	DMDD (n= 64)			Total sample (n= 2847)			aOR	95% CI
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE		
Male	33	53.4	6.2	1370	50.1	0.9	1.00	
Female	31	46.6	6.2	1477	49.9	0.9	0.78	(0.47-1.29)
Age (years)								
12	11	13.1	4.8	572	17.0	0.9		
13	16	23.5	3.7	529	16.6	0.8		
14	15	18.6	4.2	593	16.5	0.7		
15	9	14.9	5.9	424	17.2	0.8		
16	7	14.0	4.8	402	16.8	0.7		
17	6	15.9	6.6	327	15.9	0.8	0.89	(0.72-1.11)
Living with parents								
Yes (both)	34	51.7	5.8	1893	66.3	0.7	1.00	
No (One/none)	30	48.3	5.8	954	33.7	0.7	0.54*	(0.33-0.88)
Current Student								
Yes	49	75.4	6.8	2410	81.8	1.0	1.00	
No	15	24.6	6.8	437	18.2	1.0	0.66	(0.27-1.58)
Parents education								
None/Primary	13	19.3	5.3	725	25.6	0.6	1.00	
Secondary (7-9 yrs.)	27	40.7	6.2	1078	38.1	1.4	1.58	(0.71-3.49)
High School (10-12 yrs.)	12	18.9	5.3	658	22.6	0.9	0.99	(0.41-2.41)
College (13+ yrs.)	12	21.2	6.6	385	13.6	0.7	1.88	(0.51-6.98)
Parents Income								
Low	20	32.8	8.3	1106	38.9	1.3	1.00	
Average	17	25.8	7.3	883	30.9	0.9	1.05	(0.39-2.80)
High	27	41.5	5.7	858	30.2	1.0	1.65	(0.90-3.01)
Lifetime Suicidal behavior								
Ideation	18	27.9	6.2	319	11.4	0.6	1.48	(0.83-2.64)
Plan	9	15.7	5.7	102	3.7	0.4	2.20	(0.72-6.76)
Attempt	8	15.2	5.8	90	3.3	0.4	2.42	(0.70-8.40)
Any lifetime service use								
Yes	27	40.4	6.7	711	25.2	1.0	1.58	(0.81-3.09)

Note: SE = Standard error; aOR = Adjusted odds ratio, 95% CI = 95% confidence interval; *p =0.01

Comorbidity

Table 2 presents the proportion of comorbid disorders amongst those with DMDD and the proportion of those meeting the criteria for DMDD amongst those with other disorders. 94.3% of those with DMDD had a comorbid disorder, disruptive behavior disorders being the most frequent (86%), followed by anxiety disorders (72.7%), mood disorders (16.8%), and, lastly, substance use disorders (6.6%). With regards to specific disorders, the single most comorbid disorder in those who met the criteria for DMDD was intermittent explosive disorder (71.6%), followed by specific phobia (38.8%), oppositional defiant disorder (33.4%), and separation anxiety disorder (25.1%).

On the flip side, only four percent of those with any disorder also met the criteria for DMDD, 3.2% of those with a substance use disorder, 3.9% of those with any anxiety disorder, 4.7% of those with a mood disorder, and 9.3% of those with a disruptive behavior disorder. The individual disorders that had the greatest prevalence of comorbid DMDD were dysthymia (20%), intermittent explosive disorder (14.2%), and generalized anxiety disorder (11.8%). The estimation for dysthymia should be interpreted with caution as there were only two participants with dysthymia and DMDD.

Table 2. Prevalence of comorbid disorders amongst those with DMDD and % of DMDD amongst those with other disorders

	DMDD and a comorbid disorder	Among those with DMDD, % with another disorder		Among those with the following disorders, n% with DMDD	
	n	%	SE	%	SE
Panic disorder	6	6.6	2.8	6.4	3.1
Generalized anxiety disorder	2	5.5	4.4	11.8	8.4
Social phobia	14	24.4	7.3	3.8	1.0
Specific phobia	27	38.8	6.3	3.0	0.5
Agoraphobia	6	8.6	2.9	3.4	1.2
Posttraumatic stress disorder	4	7.7	4.0	9.5	4.7
Separation anxiety disorder	17	25.1	4.9	6.5	1.4
Any anxiety disorder	47	72.7	6.0	3.9	0.4
Major depressive disorder	9	16.8	4.4	4.7	1.3
Dysthymia	2	6.5	4.9	20.0	13.0

	DMDD and a comorbid disorder	Among those with DMDD, % with another disorder		Among those with the following disorders, n% with DMDD	
	n	%	SE	%	SE
Bipolar I or II	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Any mood disorder	9	16.8	4.4	4.7	1.3
Alcohol use	1	1.3	1.3	0.8	0.8
Alcohol dependence	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Drug use	2	5.4	4.4	7.2	5.8
Drug dependence	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Any substance use disorder	3	6.6	4.6	3.2	2.1
Intermittent explosive disorder	45	71.6	4.9	14.2	1.4
Oppositional defiant disorder	20	33.4	7.4	8.5	1.8
Conduct disorder	10	16.7	5.2	9.5	2.6
ADHD	7	10.1	4.0	8.9	3.3
Any impulsive disorder	54	86.0	4.2	9.3	0.9
Any internalizing disorder	50	77.7	6.1	3.9	0.5
Any externalizing disorder	54	86.0	4.2	8.3	0.8
Any disorder	60	94.3	2.7	4.0	0.4

Note: SE = Standard error.

The comorbidity pattern of those meeting the criteria for DMDD compared to those with other lifetime disorders is presented on Table 3. The first comparison is between the DMDD sample and those with any lifetime disorder. The comorbidity pattern differs between the DMDD sample and those with any other lifetime disorder only for disruptive disorders such that those with DMDD were 12 times more likely to present with a disruptive disorder than those with any other lifetime disorder (aOR= 12.00, 95% CI = 5.78 – 24.90, $p < 0.00001$). Similarly, the

DMDD sample was 17 times more likely to present with any disruptive disorder compared to those with any anxiety disorder (aOR= 16.9, 95% CI = 8.58 – 33.30, $p < 0.00001$) and more than seven times more likely to present with any disruptive disorder compared to those with any lifetime mood disorder (aOR = 7.64, 95% CI = 3.79 – 15.42, $p < 0.00001$). When comparing the DMDD sample to those with any lifetime disruptive disorder those with DMDD were 1.84 times more likely to present with any anxiety disorder (95% CI = 1.01 – 3.3, $p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Comparison of comorbidity patterns between those who meet DMDD criteria and other disorder clusters.

	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime disorder (n=1436)			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any anxiety disorder	47	72.7	6.0	1153	78.8	1.3	1.50	(0.79-2.87)	0.21
Any mood disorder	9	16.8	4.4	299	21.0	1.1	0.83	(0.44-1.54)	0.54
Any substance use disorder	3	6.6	4.6	102	8.9	1.0	0.62	(0.14-2.78)	0.52
Any impulsive disorder	54	86.0	4.2	550	39.1	1.3	12.00	(5.78-24.90)	0.00
	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime anxiety disorder (n=1153)			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any mood disorder	9	16.8	4.4	145	13.0	1.4	0.72	(0.37-1.42)	0.34
Any substance use disorder	3	6.6	4.6	61	6.4	0.9	0.62	(0.13-2.90)	0.53
Any impulsive disorder	54	86.0	4.2	342	30.5	1.5	16.90	(8.58-33.30)	0.00
	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime mood disorder (n=299) *			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any anxiety disorder	47	72.7	6.0	209	68.3	3.2	1.16	(0.50-2.68)	0.73
Any substance use disorder	3	6.6	4.6	25	9.7	2.0	0.53	(0.11-2.59)	0.42
Any impulsive disorder	54	86.0	4.2	134	47.3	2.5	7.64	(3.79-15.42)	0.00
	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime impulse disorder (n=550)			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any anxiety disorder	47	72.7	6.0	342	61.4	2.4	1.84	(1.01-3.34)	0.05
Any mood disorder	9	16.8	4.4	85	16.4	1.6	0.77	(0.40-1.46)	0.41

	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime disorder (n=1436)			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any substance use disorder	3	6.6	4.6	49	10.4	1.8	0.59	(0.13-2.71)	0.48
	Among those who meet DMDD criteria (n=64)			Among those with any lifetime substance disorder (n=102)			aOR	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Any anxiety disorder	47	72.7	6.0	61	57.0	4.9	1.70	(0.62-4.65)	0.29
Any mood disorder	9	16.8	4.4	17	17.5	4.0	0.63	(0.25-1.61)	0.33
Any impulsive disorder	54	86.0	4.2	49	45.7	5.5	7.64	(3.37-17.29)	0.00

Note: SE = Standard error; aOR = Adjusted odds ratio; 95% CI = 95% confidence interval; *includes bipolar I & II.

Age of onset

In order to evaluate whether age 10 is a meaningful cut-off for the onset of DMDD symptoms, we compared the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of those who fully met the criteria for DMDD before age 10 with those who fully met the criteria, except that onset was between the ages of 10 and 12 (see Table 4). Both groups were almost identical, except for family composition and one of the four impairment areas. Those meeting the DMDD criteria before the age of 10

were 47% less likely to live with both parents than those meeting the criteria between the ages of 10 and 12 (95% CI = 0.23 – 0.96, p=0.04). While there was no difference between the groups for impairment in household chores, school/work or social life, those meeting DMDD criteria before the age of 10 had significantly more impairment in family relations (X= 4.9, SD = 0.4) than those meeting criteria between 10 and 12 years of age (X = 3.5, SD = 0.5) (t= 2.4; p = 0.02). The overall prevalence of DMDD is 3.5% when the age of onset cut-off was extended to 12 years.

Table 4. Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of those meeting DMDD criteria before age 10 compared to those meeting criteria between the ages of 10 and 12

	Meets DMDD criteria before age 10 (n = 64)			Meets DMDD criteria (except age of onset is between 10 and 12 years) (n = 39)			OR*	95% CI	p
	n	%	SE	n	%	SE			
Sex									
Male	33	53.4	6.2	18	47.3	6.5	1.00		
Female	31	46.6	6.2	21	52.7	6.5	0.84	(0.39-1.82)	0.65
Age (years)									
12	11	13.1	4.8	3	8.6	4.9	0.83	(0.65-1.05)	0.12
13	16	23.5	3.7	7	15.0	6.5			
14	15	18.6	4.2	14	26.4	6.3			
15	9	14.9	5.9	7	22.1	7.4			
16	7	14.0	4.8	3	11.1	4.5			
17	6	15.9	6.6	5	16.9	6.0			
Living With Parents									
Yes (both)	34	51.7	5.8	25	66.8	7.2	1.00		
No (One/none)	30	48.3	5.8	14	33.2	7.2	0.47	(0.23-0.96)	0.04
Current Student									
Yes	49	75.4	6.8	31	78.9	6.5	1.00		
No	15	24.6	6.8	8	21.1	6.5	0.50	(0.22-1.12)	0.09
Parents Education									
None/Primary	13	19.3	5.3	13	35.0	10.4	1.00		
Secondary (7-9 yrs.)	27	40.7	6.2	15	38.5	11.0	2.12	(0.57-7.90)	
High School (10-12 yrs.)	12	18.9	5.3	7	17.5	6.3	2.47	(0.67-9.11)	
College (13+ yrs.)	12	21.2	6.6	4	9.1	5.0	3.95	(0.52-29.91)	0.47
Parents income									
Low	20	32.8	8.3	16	44.0	9.1	1.00		
Average	17	25.8	7.3	14	33.8	10.8	1.35	(0.23-7.74)	
High	27	41.5	5.7	9	22.1	6.5	2.93	(0.79-10.89)	0.25
Lifetime suicidal behavior									
Ideation	18	27.9	6.2	12	30.2	8.4	0.53	(0.17-1.66)	0.27
Plan	9	15.7	5.7	3	9.2	4.8	4.04	(0.40-41.07)	0.23
Attempt	8	15.2	5.8	5	12.6	5.1	1.31	(0.22-7.67)	0.76
Any lifetime service use									
Yes	27	40.4	6.7	12	35.3	8.8	1.59	(0.49-5.12)	0.43

Note: SE = Standard error; aOR = Adjusted odds ratio; 95% CI = 95% confidence interval.

When we compared the comorbidity pattern of those who met the DMDD criteria before age 10 as stipulated in DSM-5 and those who met the criteria with onset between the ages of 10 and 12, there were no significant differences in the proportion of any comorbid disorders.

DISCUSSION

Prevalence

According to the main purpose of our research, the prevalence of DMDD estimated in this community sample combining both youth and parent reports was 2.18%. While most of those with DMDD have a comorbid disorder (94.3 %), among all the participants with any psychiatric disorder only a small proportion have DMDD (4.0 %). Raising the cut-off for the age of onset to 12 years of age, increases the prevalence to 3.5%.

The prevalence reported in this study is very similar to the rates reported previously in community samples, which ranged from 0.8% to 3.3% (8). We only evaluated adolescents in our sample which constitutes a significant difference to the other studies which primarily included pre-school and school aged children. These earlier studies indicate a greater prevalence in younger children which might suggest an even lower prevalence in an adolescent sample. On the other hand, given the likely persistent nature of DMDD and the low service use for mental health conditions in Mexico (27) it is not surprising that our prevalence estimation is closer to the upper limit of the previous reports.

Sociodemographic characteristics

Living in mono-parental families was the unique clinical difference between those with DMDD and the whole sample. This characteristic might be linked to less behavioral control and supervision in single parent households, thus potentially contributing to more temper tantrums and irritability; another possible explanation might be that the stress caused by having a child with this condition impacts the marital relationship and the likelihood of separation, or if there is a genetic vulnerability for DMDD, the greater likelihood of having a parent with this condition might contribute to marital disruptions (28-29). In this regard, published research showed that chronic irritability in preschool-age children was associated with parental depression and anxiety (30); furthermore, the same group showed in another publication that parental lifetime substance use disorder and higher parental hostility when the children were aged three, were predictors for DMDD at age six (31). It is likely that emotion regulation difficulties may be a marker of severity in subjects with psychopathology, including first degree relatives. In this sense, interestingly besides phobias, separation anxiety disorder (children-mother attachment category) was the most frequent (25%) anxiety disorder in this group.

Delimitation from other disorders

Taking into consideration the possibility of double counting for those cases with DMDD and IED as the most common comorbidity, our data suggests that DMDD and IED disorders are distinguishable from each other; while a major propor-

tion (71.6%) of those with DMDD met the IED criteria, only a minor proportion (14.2%) of those with IED met the DMDD criteria. If the high comorbidity with IED was simply an effect of double counting, given that many of the questions for the DMDD criteria came from the IED section of the CIDI, we would expect the same high comorbidity with ODD from which an equal number of questions was obtained, but this was not the case. These results have implications for the DSM-5, especially for criterion J; if we were to exclude those with IED and ODD from those diagnosed with DMDD, virtually none would remain; retaining those with comorbid MDD seems to force the grouping of DMDD into affective disorders. The comorbidity pattern of those with DMDD found in this study does not support the decision of DSM-5 to incorporate DMDD into the depressive disorder cluster, but rather supports the idea that this disorder is more clearly associated to disruptive behavioral categories as a distinct disorder or at least as a specifier for disruptive behavior disorders. These results are more consistent with the ICD-11 working group that had considered classifying chronic irritability as a specifier across the different disruptive behavioral disorders and not just ODD (30). Chronic irritability has been reported as part of the three factors integrating the ODD construct (33). Confirmatory factor analysis supports the connection between ODD and emotional dysregulation and not ODD and CD (34). This may be attributed to ODD serving as a bridge disorder in classification between externalizing and internalizing dimensions. Even more, the global field study developed in 48 countries by the WHO found that compared to ICD-10 and DSM-5, ICD-11 led to more accurate identifica-

tion of severe irritability and better differentiation from boundary presentations. Participants using DSM-5 largely failed to apply the DMDD diagnosis when it was appropriate, and they more often applied psychopathological diagnosis to developmentally normative irritability (35).

Cut-off age point

Additionally, the DSM-5 did not state its rationale for establishing the age of 10 years as a cut-off for symptom onset. We therefore compared those meeting the established age-of-onset cut-off and those having symptom onset after 10 years of age, but before 13 years. We found no differences in the comorbidity pattern or other clinically relevant characteristics, suggesting no meaningful reason for age 10 being the cut-off. Additionally, those with the higher age threshold were just as impaired (in three of four domains) as those with the current DSM-5 age threshold. Raising the age cut-off to 12 years, however, does represent an important increase in prevalence from 2.2% to 3.5%, which means the current age cut-off excludes an important youth group that may benefit from timely diagnosis and treatment. It makes more sense to set the age of onset threshold at 12 years since this marks the end of childhood and is consistent with what was done for ADHD in DSM-5.

Limitations

The main limitation of this study is that it is a secondary data analysis of a survey which was not designed to establish a DMDD diagnosis. Data was obtained mainly from the ODD and IED items of the CIDI which may constitute a methodological bias towards

greater comorbidity with these disorders over depressive disorders from which only a few items were incorporated into the algorithm. However, a comparable number of items was taken from the IED section and from the ODD section, and yet there is greater comorbidity with IED than ODD. Also, we were not able to evaluate two of the DSM-5 DMDD criteria, namely, criterion B (that temper outbursts are inconsistent with development level), and criterion E (the duration criterion). Had we been able to include these two criteria, our prevalence estimate would probably be lower. The cross-sectional design limits any determination of the direction of associations. Finally, we were only able to evaluate two of the five phases to validate the diagnostic categories proposed by Robins and Guze; some other phases have been studied in a recent DMDD *post hoc* analysis (2) and also for limited prosocial emotions (36) recommended as a specifier for CD in DSM-5 and probably in disruptive conduct disorders in ICD-11 (37).

Despite these limitations, given that scientific evidence for this controversial new diagnosis is scarce and centered on child samples from the United States, this study provides novel data from a representative population survey of adolescents from a Latin American country.

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